

DIMPA CHAKRAIN ASTROLOGY
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Abstract:

Man born in the earth, in his life period, used everything created by nature according to his desire, either by reforming them or not reforming them. Also, right from the beginning, he has made developments for somethings in nature and brought few things in the nature in a new shape by destruction. Nature has attained evolution either by natural means or by artificial means by the mankind for his needs. As long as the sun family and mankind exist. This will continue. The rituals and customs are also subjected to this evolution. Traditionally whatever discovered by the mankind and as per the circumstances, the Astrological science has been improved without reforming its taproot. This astrological science has many subsects within it. But prediction in all the subsects of astrology is given by position of Sun, Moon other five planets, and Ragu, Ketu. To find out when and where the obstacles will come in the life time, how to cross over, what is the karma in this birth, how to handle this karma carefully, what are the responsibilities in this birth, Dimpa Chakra is helpful by considering the Rasi Chart as body and by the help of Planets and position order of the stars.

Key Words: Nakshatra, Graha, Human Body Parts, Dimpa Chakra.

Introduction:

Dimpa is Sanskrit word. The meaning of Dimpa is "Infant". Prediction of the horoscope of a person is done on the basis of finding the part of the body where the birthstar, on which Moon is located. This is done by starting with the star of the Sun, the leader of solar system, and placing it in series in the body of the person. Sun gives the power of light to all living beings in the universe. Sun is the Paternal planet. Sun gives the Life and soul to the body. Moon gives body to the soul. If there is no body, no soul will exist. Hence the birthstar where the moon stood is also considered important.

Method of Forming Dimpa Chakra:

डिम्पाख्यचक्रेरविभाच्चभानां त्रयं न्यरोन्मूधिनमुखेत्रयञ्च।
द्वेस्कन्धयोद्वेभुजयोद्वयंचपाणिद्वयेवक्षसिपञ्चभानि।।
नाभौचलिङ्गोचतथैकमेकंद्वजानुनोःपदायुगेभष्टकम्।
पुंसासदावैपरिकल्पनीयं मुनिप्रवर्येफलमुक्तमत्र।।

By listing the star in proper sequence where Sun stood (located), placing the parts of the body Viz, Forehead, Face, Shoulder, Chest, Naval, Forearms (R and L), Genital organ, Hands, Thighs (R and L), Feet, in series, prediction is done on the basis where the Moon is located in the parts of the body along with the concerned star.

Method of Fixing Central Points of Dimpa Chakra in the Twelve Houses:

Places	Body Parts	Stars
1 st Lagna	Forehead	3- Stars
2 nd	Face	3- Stars
3 rd	Shoulder	2- Stars
4 th	Chest	5- Stars
5 th	Naval	1- Stars
6 th	Right Shoulder	1- Stars
7 th	Left Shoulder	1- Stars
8 th	Private part	1- Stars
9 th	Hands	2- Stars
10 th	Right Thigh	1- Stars
11 th	Left Thigh	1- Stars
12 th	Feet	6-Stars

Dimpa Chakra Rasi Chart:

Pisces ¹² Feet-6	Aries Lagna ¹ Fore Head-3	Taurus ² Face-3	Gemini ³ Shoulder-2
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Aquarius ¹¹ Left thigh-1	Rasi Chart		Cancer ⁴ Chest-5
Capricorn ¹⁰ Right thigh-1			Leo ⁵ Navel-1
Sagittarius ⁹ Hand-2	Scorpio ⁸ Private Part-1	Libra ⁷ Left Shoulder-1	Virgo ⁶ Right Shoulder-1

Prediction by Dimba Chakra when the birth Star Is Located:

सद्रत्नचमीकरचारुवस्रविचित्रबालव्यजनातपत्रैः।

विराजमानोमनुजोनितान्तमौलिस्थलेभनलिनीप्रभोश्चेत्॥

- **Forehead:** When the birth star is located at Fore head, that person will be crowned. It will yield good results. The person will live a luxurious life with dignity in the society. He will acquire top posts with lot of responsibilities in his career and will guide many. He will have a good character and blessed life.

मिष्टाशनानांशयनासनानभोक्ताचवक्तासततंप्रसन्नः॥

स्मिताननोवावदनानुयांतभानोर्भवेध्दजननेहियस्य॥

- **Face:** He will be always cheerful. He will not show the sadness in his face. He will wish to have a luxurious dress, food and stay. He will have a smiling face. He will be good orator.

वृषांशकोवंशविभूषणश्चमहोत्सवार्थप्रथितःप्रतापी।

नरोऽतिशूरोऽतिरामुदारोदिवाकरोऽस्थितमंसकेचेत्॥

- **Shoulder:** He will help others and hence will be blessed person. He will conduct the festivals in the religious places. He would like to wear ornaments.

त्यक्तस्वदेशःपुरुषोविशोषादगर्वाध्दतःशौर्ययुतोनितान्तम्।

विदेशवासाप्तमहत्प्रतिष्ठोमार्तण्डभंबाहुगतंप्रसूतौ॥

- **Shoulder: (Arms)** He will be living and residing away from his birth place. He will be living in abroad or other states. By the other contacts he will be highly benefitted financially and personally.

वदान्यतासद्गुणवर्जितश्चपण्यादिरन्तादिपरिक्षकश्च।

सत्यानृताभ्यांसहितोहिमर्त्योदिवामणेर्भयदिपाणिसंस्थम्॥

- **Hands:** He will attract all by his speeches. He will have high sense of humor. He will have the expertise in evaluating gem stones. He will achieve his goals. He is skilled and experienced in talking according to the suitability of time.

भुपालतुल्यःस्वकुलेसुशीलोबालोविशालोत्तमकीर्तिशाली।

शास्त्रेप्रवीणःपरिसुतिकालेवक्षस्थलेचेन्नलिनीशभंस्यात्॥

- **Chest:** He will be from a prestigious family hereditary. He will be a scholar in all rituals and religious customs. He will be honest person. He will have extraordinary wisdom in spiritual, preacher and will be praised by all.

क्षमासमेतोरणकर्मभीरुःकलाकलापाकलनैकशीलः।

धर्मप्रवृत्तिःसुतरामुदारोनाभीसरोजेऽम्बुजबन्धुतारा॥

- **Navel:** He will fight for the justice. He will not support injustice. He will be great executor and will have the quality of forgiving others. He will have religious faiths.

कन्दर्पधुर्योऽज्झितसाधुकर्मासङ्गीतनृत्याभिरुचिःकलाजः।

चेज्जन्मकालेनलिनीशभंस्याद्गुह्यस्थलेसोऽतुलकीर्तियुक्तः॥

- **Private part:** He will have a charming face and will attract others. He will be pious and also will be lustful. He will be good at arts, dialogues, dance and acting. He will be highly talented and will be appreciated by all.

नानादेशानेकधासम्प्रचारःकार्योत्साहश्चजलःक्षामगात्रः।

धूर्तोमर्त्यःसत्यहीनश्चनूनजानुस्थानेभानुभंजन्मानिस्यात्॥

- **Thigh:** He will travel a lot and hence will have a lean body. He will be good executing his activities.

कृषिक्रियायानिरतोऽल्पधर्मःशत्रूज्झितःसेवनकर्मकर्ता।

तारायदिस्यादरविन्दबन्धोःपादारविन्देचनरस्यसूतौ॥

- **Feet:** He will be having his career in manufacturing, business and agriculture. He will carry out all activities with courage. He will execute public related activities.

Method of prediction from Lagna to all 12 Bhavas in Dimba Chakra:

Lagna: In Rasi Chakra, importance is given to Lagna. All Dhimba Chakra Lagnas will have to be taken as Forehead. Sun will always be present in lagna as sun is considered prime and as the star is taken into consideration where Sun stood. Hence Sun is not considered for the prediction. But the Lord of the house or Lord of the house of Lagna is considered. According to the Karagas of the planets in the Lagna, it is to be predicted whether it is achievement or disaster. For example, when good planet Guru is in Lagna, the person will be good in spiritual, honest, straightforward and will be good guide to those seek him. He will be good ruler, judge and will be good and useful to the society. When bad planets Saturn, Ketu, Mars is in Lagna, he will be a good person who will do all evil deeds which is bad for the society.

Second Bhava: Face is considered significant in Second Bhava. With benefic planets, the person will be lucky and will have a luxurious life and good income. With malefic planets, scars, injuries, skin problems in the face will indicate the sufferings. No income and poverty in the family. Relationship in the family will be dissatisfactory. With both benefic and malefic planets, he will face ups and downs in life. With benefic planets like Jupiter, Mercury, Moon and Venus, he will earn in an honest way. On the other hand with the malefic planets Ragu, Ketu, Saturn and Mars, he earned illegally and greediness will lead him to the improper way of life.

Third Bhava: Third Bhava is in Shoulder. Third Bhava is "burden". It depends on the good or bad planets in the third Bhava that what burdens we have brought from last birth and what burdens we are carrying to next birth. More over. If the moon, which is the center of Dimba Chakra, is in Third Bhava, it is believed that that person will nullify his karma in this birth and will reach God without further more birth. Specialty of the third Bhava is, good planets should be in the third Bhava for beneficial predictions by all astrologers he visits. We are being born again to compensate our deeds in last births. The third Bhava helps to discover the purpose of this birth. If Jupiter, Venus, Moon and Mercury is in third Bhava, there is not much karma effect in this birth. By visiting temples, the karma effect can be set right. If Moon is in third Bhava, Goddess Ambal temple is to be visited. If Venus is in third Bhava, Goddess Lakshmi temple is to be visited. If Jupiter is in third Bhava, God Shiva temple, Sidhar peedam is to be visited. If Mercury is in third Bhava, Vaishnava temple is to be visited.

Those who have good planets in third Bhava will do their duty without bias with sincerity and service mentality. For most of the top-ranking Officials. Third Bhava will have good planets. Teachers will take fullest efforts for the progress of the students. If husband or wife has the good planets in third Bhava will shoulder the difficulties and will take part in happiness or agony of the partners.

At the Same Time, Following will be Results for those who have Bad Planets in their Third Bhava:

- They will have the idea of marrying but will lead life individually without marrying.
- They will not have satisfaction in their married life feel the married life as burden.
- They will not be blessed with children or will not be happy with children,
- Even they work hard and sincere, they will not be recognized by the employer and will be rejected by others.
- They cannot repay the loans even after struggling hard.
- They will give surety for other's loan and will suffer.
- Even if they work with responsibility, selflessly and sincerely, they will not earn good name in the family.
- They will endure with the ailments throughout the life.
- They will not get any positive results even taking much efforts.
- Those who have Saturn, Mars, Ragu, Ketu, either combined or single in the third bhava cannot rectify the karma even after visiting temples. They will have to undergo all suffering till karma is nullified.
- If good and bad planets are in the third bhava, good and bad incidents will happen alternately.

Fourth Bhava: Fourth bhava indicates about mother, heart, house, agricultural land, land with water table, relatives, arts, vehicle. The fourth bhava is chest and if moon presents in the Dimba Chakra centre part of Fourth bhava, that person will be a kind hearted.

- As they long for love and affection they are born to rectify the karma of being a separatist and not a family loving person in the last birth.
- They will show pure love.
- They will be highly emotional.
- They cannot bear the separation of one they love.
- They will even suicide when not able to bear the separation and even may go to an extent to kill one goes away from them.
- They will be highly knowledgeable in all arts, science and rituals will be expert in giving opinion and guidance for everything.

As moon lies in the heart in fourth bhava, they will believe who speaks loving words and will fall in love. They will get cheated and lose their belongings easily.

Fifth Bhava: In Dimba Chakra, when moon is located in the centre of fifth bhava, it indicates stomach. Navel denotes the relationship between mother and child. This fifth bhava indicates arts, profession. For those this fifth bhava is good, they will lead a comfortable and rich life.

- If Mercury is present in the fifth bhava, considered to be stomach
- in Dimba Chakra, that person will be highly knowledgeable in education.
- If Jupiter is present in the fifth bhava of Dimba Chakra, he will have good teaching capability.
- If Saturn, Ragu, Ketu and Mars present in the fifth bhava of Dimba Chakra, even if he studies well, he cannot score good marks. Even if he works hard, he cannot come up in life. Even if he studies all books, he will not be able to understand astrology. Even if he is talented he will not get any opportunity. He cannot repay his debts for ever, will not get food, he will be in poverty, he will be with ailments and will not be peaceful in life.
- This presence of these planets is the root cause for gas trouble, hernia, cancer tumour and troubles in the body.

Sixth Bhava: In Dimba Chakra, when moon is located in the centre of sixth bhava, it indicates shoulder of right hand. The right shoulder of sixth bhava indicates masculinity. He will overcome enemy as well as diseases.

If Mars and Ragu present single or combined,

- Nobody can defeat him.
- Enemies will be scared of him.
- All accusations and cases will be quashed.
- They will be expert in the medical field especially in surgery.
- He will be extraordinary in all sports and games.
- He will be an expert in maneuvering the vehicles in land, water and air.
- No sickness will attack him and he will be very hard working.

If Saturn or Ketu joined with Mars or Ragu is present in the right shoulder, it will give negative results. The sixth place is considered to be the place of enemy. When Jupiter is present in the sixth place, he will be getting rid of lust, enmity with others, and will not have any strong desire for anything. He will be with good vices and will live like Yogis. If Venus is present in sixth place, he will be attracted to opposite genders. Hence, he should be careful not to go into wrong path. If Mercury is present in sixth place, he will be having more mental power than physical power. Hence, he will be highly knowledgeable and will reach high positions in life.

Seventh Bhava: The seventh Bhava in Dimba Chakra with moon as central point indicates shoulder of left hand. As this shoulder (seventh bhava) indicates the place of Husband and wife, it also specifies about the ethics of husband and wife in the family life. If the Planet Venus is in seventh bhava, it reveals that he will get married soon and also the husband and wife will live with unity always. If Mercury is in seventh place, he will get benefits from in-law and father-in-law and also he will be successful in the business through wife.

- If Jupiter is in seventh bhava, He will have divine family life and he had been blessed in the last birth.
- The life partner is like God. The couples will lead life like lovers.
- He will be fortunate after marriage. He will not leave his life partner.
- If Saturn, Mars, Ragu or Ketu with Mars and Ketu with Saturn in the seventh place, He will get troubles after marriage and will hate life partner.
- He will be afraid of living with life partner.
- Even with remarriage the married life will not be stable.
- He will be worrying that he is not getting married.
- He will feel that marriage is the curse of last birth.
- He will lament that life has turned negative after marriage.
- He will get married without the consent of parents and relatives.
- He will get married to the life partner from other caste.
- He will not like to get married.
- He will have illegal affairs.
- He will dislike family life and flee from the house.

Eighth Bhava in the Dimba Chakra: The eighth place indicates husband, wife, genital organ and lust. If Moon with Ragu or Moon with Ketu, or Mars, or Saturn or Ragu or Ketu is present in the eighth place, he or she will have sexual harassment troubles like rape. They will have uterus problems, problems in the genital organ, and sexually transmitted diseases. They will be lustful with illegal affair and face many obstacles for marriage. If Venus alone is present in eighth place, it gives more benefits in the family life. It gives a pleasant family life and long life. If Jupiter is in the eighth place, they will overcome the lustful feelings.

He will be a great person and children will also be great. The Jupiter in the eighth place will control the sperm and helps to reach God.

Ninth Bhava in the Dimba Chakra: The result will be same as for the sixth and seventh place which indicates the shoulders of the Hands. If moon is present in the ninth place and seen by Jupiter, he will be involved in the spiritual deeds like consecrations, prayers and offerings.

Tenth Bhava in the Dimba Chakra: The Tenth place indicates the right thigh. It is told that right thigh is feature of deity Kali. If Mars is present in the tenth place, he will be high will power, mental power, physical power. He will do heroic deeds and will be specialised and will achieve in the field of medicines, army, sports, transports and architecture. At the same time if Mars is at Exalted or Debilitated or Mars joined with Ragu it will yield bad effects in the life.

Eleventh Bhava in Dimba Chakra: Eleventh Bhava is located in Left Thigh. He will be the right person to start or inaugurate the ceremonies like purchasing gold for wedding chains, ploughing, planting, harvesting, borewell drilling, foundation laying for buildings. They are highly fortunate to become millionaires and always luck will favour them.

Twelfth Bhava in Dimba Chakra: This is located in the foot. This is not the place of draining or wasting money and on the other hand, it helps a person to get settled and achieve in this world. If Jupiter is in the Twelfth place, he will travel across seas and will achieve. Jupiter will lead in spiritual path. Planets Venus, Mercury, New moon will give luxurious life.

These planets will support to achieve in Cinema field, Writing, Irrigation field and in rituals. Sun will support to shine in the politics and medical sciences. Mars will support to achieve in the fields of Construction, Electricity, Military, Police. It will be good if the planet present in this place is either naturally good or good planet who is the owner of this house. It will not be good if Ragu or Ketu is present in this 12th place.

Method to diagnose the diseases by Dimba Chakra:

The effects of the disease depend on the planet situated in the parts of the body and if there is impact of bad planets like Ragu and Ketu, that part of the body will get disease and will get affected.

- **Sun:** indicates Forehead and hence fever, eye problems, bone fracture and diseases related to bone, head ache, heat diseases, heart attack will occur. During the transit (Kocharam) of bad planets cross over and stays with Sun, symptoms of all these diseases appear.
- **Moon:** Sleeplessness, mental diseases, menstruation problems, sexually transmitted diseases, skin diseases, Tuberculosis, Sinus trouble, fits and typhoid will attack. During the transit (Kocharam) of bad planets cross over and stays with Moon, symptoms of all these diseases appear.
- **Mars:** Burns, Weapon injury, Dog bite, accident, blood pressure, Bile, anaemia, heart problems will attack.
- **Mercury:** Leprosy, Infertility, stomach problems, skin diseases, itching, throat problems, baldness, dumb, Leukoderma will happen.
- **Jupiter:** Kidneys, Ears, Spleen, liver, hepatitis, piles, hernia, lungs problems will attack.
- **Venus:** Face related diseases, diabetics, kidney problems, eye problems, sexually transmitted diseases, skin diseases, abortion will occur.
- **Saturn:** Leg problems, knee joint problems, Rheumatoid, mental problems, laziness, gas troubles, stammering, wounds, asthma, indigestion, dental problems will attack.
- **Raku:** Skin diseases, Smallpox, cancer, leprosy, asthma, spleen problems, allergy, stammering, sudden death, murder, accident, sexual assault, homosexual, snakebite, attack by animals, mental retardation will happen.
- **Ketu:** Stomach problem will happen.

In Dimba chakra in all the twelve Bhavas, the diseases can either be diagnosed by taking the Bhavas into consideration and the stars present in the Bhavas:

Disease curing period in Dimba Chakra:

- By looking into the stars in the Dimba chakra, it can be predicted when disease will attack and how long will it take to cure.
- When disease comes in Aswini Star, it will get cured within twenty-five days. When disease comes in Kritika Star, it will get cured within a minimum of seven days and maximum of twenty-seven days.
- When disease comes in Rohini Star, it will get cured within eight to eleven days.
- When disease comes in Mrigasira Star, it will get cured within six to seven days.
- When disease comes in Punar vasu Star, it will get cured within a minimum of fifteen days and maximum of twenty-seven days.
- When disease comes in Pushya Star, it will get cured within seven days.
- When disease comes in Purva Phalguni Star, it will get cured within seven days.
- When disease comes in Uttara Phalguni Star, it will get cured within a minimum of nine days and maximum of twenty-one days.

- When disease comes in HastaStar, it will get cured within a minimum of seven days and maximum of twenty days.
- When disease comes in ChitraStar, it will get cured within a minimum of eight days and maximum of twenty days.
- When disease comes in SwathiStar, it will get cured within a minimum of ten days and maximum of forty-five days.
- When disease comes in MoolaStar, it will get cured within a minimum of ten days and maximum of twenty-seven days.
- When disease comes in Purva AshadaStar, it will get cured within a minimum of nine days and maximum of eight or nine months.
- When disease comes in ShravanaStar, it will get cured within a minimum of eight months and maximum of twelve months.
- When disease comes in SadhabishekStar, it will get cured within thirteen days.
- When disease comes in Uttara BhadraStar, it will get cured within a minimum of fourteen days and maximum of many years.
- When disease comes in RevathiStar, it will get cured within a minimum of eight to fourteen days and maximum of twenty-seven days.
- In case disease comes in the birth star or the stars from 3rd, 5th 7th from birth star, the effect of disease will be maximum. If disease comes on Sunday, the Chaturthi thithi with stars Ardra, Ashlesha, Maga, continuous treatment will be required.
- On Tuesday as Navami thithi with the stars Jyeshtha Swati Bharani, On Saturday as Chaturdasi thithi with the stars Purva Phalguni, Purva Ashada and Purva Bhadra, treatment for diseases is required.

Stars and Days favourable for treatment

- Monday – Hasta
- Wednesday – Ashwini
- Thursday – Chitra
- Friday – Punarvasu

Ukka Yoga Days - (Particular Stars and Tithi's Joining days)

Stars	Tithi's
Rohini	Tritiya, Navami
Uttara Phalguni	Chaturthi
Shravana	Panchami
Mrigasira	Shasthi
Revati	Saptami
Krittika	Navami
Pushya	Dasami
Anuradha	Dwadasi, Tritiya
Magha	Trayodasi

If treatment is taken on Ukka Yoga days, the diseases will get cured. Moreover, it will be very special when Moon Mercury Venus Jupiter are in the ruling house and as Fixed sign, Mutable Lagna or Navamsa. Treatment for those who are affected by contagious disease like Malaria, Measles, Respiratory illness and infection fever on Sunday with thithi's Navami Chaturthi Chaturdasi can be started. But the star of that day should not be Bharani, Ardra and Vishaka.

Favourable Days for Surgery:

- Waxing moon period is suitable for surgery. Surgery should be avoided in the days of Amavasya and when the moon comes to the birth Rasi. Tues day and Saturday are good for undergoing surgery. Mars star should be strong and the eighth house should be in good position to do the surgery. When Ardra star coincides with Chaturthi thithi, Jyeshtha star combine with Navami thithi and Ashlesha or Mula coincides with Trayodasi thithi, it is favourable for doing surgeries.
- An important point to be noted is that when the day of disease and the star of disease days known, then only we can predict how long the treatment is to be taken for curing the disease. In certain rules, when the benefic planets like Jupiter, Mercury Venus and Moon is present, the disease will get cured. On the other hand, it is found from the researches that if the malefic planets like Saturn, Mars, Ragu, Ketu are present, the duration of curing period differs.

Example Horoscope:

Rasi Chart
 Date of Birth: 11-08-1974.
 Time of Birth: 10-11-27 Pm

Lagna		Moon, Ketu	Saturn
Jupiter ®	Rasi Chart		Venus, Mercury Sun
			Mars
	Ragu		

Placement of Padas (Padasaram):

Planets	Naksatras	Place in Dimba Chakra
Sun	Ashlesha	Fore Head – 1
Moon	Krittika	Feet - 12
Mars	Purva Phalguni	Fore Head - 1
Mercury	Ashlesha	Fore Head - 1
Venus	Pushya	Feet - 12
Saturn	Punarvasu	Feet - 12
Ragu	Jyeshtha	Chest - 4
Ketu	Mrigasira	Feet - 12
Jupiter	Purva Bhadra	Private part - 8

Dimba Chakra Rasi Chart:

Sun Mercury Mars			Ragu
Moon Venus Saturn Ketu	Dimba Chakra Rasi Chart		
			Jupiter

Let us have the Prediction of the Given Model Horoscope by the method of Dimba Chakra:

- As the sun is present in the Lagna as first house, it shows that the person will face anything with courage and he will be uniqueness in his deeds and he will be honest person.
- The planet of the seventh house, the Mercury is in in Lagna with Sun. It indicates maternal uncle and friends. He will be taught and trained by his uncle and his uncle will guide and philosopher to carry out the profession effectively. will be having lot of friends.
- The knowledge of Mathematics from Mercury and skill of architecture obtained from Mars will enable him to occupy the profession related to his education through his maternal uncle. He is skilled in designing the buildings, offices and workshops.
- Planet Ragu which has the aspect of fourth view, will make him expert in designing heavy trucks like JCP.
- Ragu which is present in the fourth place in the Dimba Chakra in Chest, will create obstacles and delay in getting helps from relatives. He will be addicted to drugs and sex from his young age. It will instigate even to suicide.
- The planet Jupiter is present in the eighth place which is Libra in the house of Venus and in the genital organ. Although it will be beneficial when Jupiter is present in eighth place in Dimba Chakra, Jupiter is the eighth view aspects of Mars. It will degrade his honor. He will not be able to keep his words. He will not be able repay his loans and will lead to an indisciplinary life. His liver will be affected and he will suffer by jaundice.
- The aspect of Jupiter as fifth view to the twelfth place considered as feet, where Venus, Moon and Saturn are present will lead to attain great fame and achievements. His spouse will tackle all his problems and will support him by functioning effectively in the business and administration. His children will also support him like that.
- The planets Venus, Moon and Saturn present in the twelfth place in Dimba Chakra, will lead to habits of consuming drugs and relations with prostitutes. This will result in drainage of wealth and irregularity in attending the job. He cannot repay his debts, will have sleepless days, and will become a psycho. But by the view aspect of Jupiter, he will get cured from psychological disorders by treatment and will look after his family and profession in a good manner.

Conclusion:

By using the Dimba Chakra, on the basis of the birth time and horoscope of a person, from the fore head that is considering the Sun as prime planet and by placing some specific stars of specific quantity with some specific parts of the body, and by converting these into Dimba Chakra it with the parts of the body, the solution for all problems of the person can be found out. When the prediction is done on the basis of star in Sun of a horoscope, it is known as Chutchuma Dimba Chakra. When the prediction is done by converting the birth time horoscope into the parts of the body, it is called Rasi Dimba Chakra. When prediction is done by noting the

movement of the planets (Kochaaram), considering the Janma Lagna, and noting which planet is in which part is called Kochara Dimba Chakra and it is the best way of prediction. Moreover, noting down the star on which Sun stood and starting from that star and placing them in sequence as per Dimba Chakra rule, and doing prediction is called Chutchuma Kochara Dimba Chakra Method. The way how the prediction is done for birth time horoscope, in the same way in Dimba Chakra, all the twelve parts will lead the Dasha every year and in each part will lead the Phuthi each month. Dimba Chakra is useful and helps to predict in all angles to solve and set right the problems in his life which cannot be predicted. The ancient books have also mentioned about this.

References:

1. Bala Bhadra "Hora Ratnam", English translation and Notes by: R. Santhanam.
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